

ROTATIONAL EFFECTS ON LOW PRESSURE TURBINE TRANSITION AND LOSSES

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ABSTRACT

The effect of the Coriolis forces on the transition mechanism of low-pressure turbines is numerically studied using a compact high-order Flux Reconstruction method using implicit LES. The method is validated using stationary experimental and fundamental DNS analyses. It is seen that Coriolis forces tend to destabilise the suction-side bubble shear layer slightly accelerating the transition to turbulence. The wake is also modified and the combined effect is a small increase in losses with respect to the baseline case. Although the analysis has several simplifying hypothesis it is believed that the engineering impact in LPT two-dimensional flows is small.

INTRODUCTION

The efficiency of modern Low-Pressure Turbines (LPTs) is controlled by the separation, transition and reattachment of the flow in the suction side of the airfoils [1]. Due to the high aspect ratio of these airfoils, 2D losses account for up to 80% of the total losses and therefore its determination is deemed of paramount importance for the design of LPTs.

At low Reynolds numbers modern LPTs exhibit a laminar separation bubble which forms a shear layer that rolls up due Kelvin-Helmholtz instabilities and typically breakdown into turbulence. The behaviour of the separation and transition is strongly dependent on the Reynolds number and the inflow con-

ditions (see for instance [1, 2, 3, 4] to name a few). Because of its complexity researchers have attempted to understand the different transition mechanisms separating different effects. Examples of this can be seen in [3, 4, 1, 2].

Lou and Hourmouziadis [3] explain the transition process in modern LPTs with steady and periodic-unsteady inlet flow conditions. Under steady conditions they identify up to five regions in the loss-generating characteristics of LPT airfoils depending on the Reynolds number. The different regions are characterised by the position of the breakdown process. At the lowest Reynolds numbers the breakdown happens downstream of the trailing edge (TE) and the suction-side bubble remains open generating a large amount of losses. As the Reynolds is increased the breakdown and transition point move upstream over the airfoil and reattachment occurs which closes the bubble and reduces the generated losses. Further increasing the Reynolds shortens the bubble and a larger attached turbulent boundary layer (BL) exists. In this latter region losses vary little with Reynolds number. A final regime is achieved at (very) high Reynolds numbers in which turbulent transition happens before the laminar separation point and an attached turbulent BL over increasing portions of the airfoil increase losses. Under periodic-unsteady mean inlet flow conditions they found that the laminar separation point remains fixed whereas transition and reattachment points vary with the phase of the mean flow perturbation with a phase shift that depends on the Strouhal number. The net effect is a time-averaged shorter laminar separation bubble.

The behaviour of transition previously discussed is heavily modified by inflow disturbances. Hodson and Howell [1] studied the effect of incoming wakes on transition and losses and later

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Coull and Hodson [2] studied the effect of incoming wakes along with background turbulence. Inlet turbulent fluctuations generate streaky disturbances in the BL called Klebanoff streaks which originate close to the leading edge (LE) where the BL thickness is lower and their receptivity higher. Klebanoff streaks interact with the Kelvin-Helmholz (KH) disturbances and promote transition. Incoming wakes generate stronger Klebanoff streaks which intensify the latter effect. Additionally, wakes can excite KH instabilities further promoting breakdown of these and transition to turbulence.

Effective design of LPTs must account for the effects of transition previously discussed. Most design processes today rely on simulations based on the Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) equations which require of models to account for turbulent effects. All RANS models, without exception, fail to properly account for this complex physical problem which requires of code calibration in order to properly predict turbine capacity and losses. Higher fidelity simulations such as DNS (Direct Navier Stokes/Direct Numerical Simulation) and LES (Large Eddy Simulation) avoid the problem of turbulence model calibration since they compute all (DNS) or most (LES) of the turbulent scales. Unlike RANS (which models all scales of turbulence) only the smallest turbulent scales are modelled in LES by a sub-grid scale (SGS) model. Larger scales dominate the mean flow whereas smaller scales are assumed independent of the large flow motions, isotropic and homogeneous, hence, easier to model. Homogeneity is lost near the walls and so more sophisticated SGS models need to be employed [5, 6, 7, 8].

Both DNS and LES have been applied to LPT cases for a variety of Reynolds numbers and inlet flow conditions, e.g., [9, 10, 4, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17].

Michelassi et al. investigated in [10] the ability of LES to capture the effect of incoming wakes on transition in an LPT. Even though the main flow features were captured in their simulation the transition process was not fully captured being the transition point $10\%c_x$ downstream with respect to that of the DNS by Wu and Durbin [17]. They attributed these differences to a rather coarse mesh and to the SGS model used in their simulations.

The effect of free inlet turbulence on the profile losses was analysed by Medic and Sharma in [11] for an array of Reynolds numbers. In their work three airfoils with different loading distribution were analysed and their numerical results compared against experimental data. For every Reynolds number and inlet turbulence intensities their LES simulations underpredicted the pressure losses. This was mainly due to the difficulty in capturing the closing of the separation bubble. Nevertheless, the simulations predicted the trends and the authors concluded that LES can be used to assess new airfoil designs and study the flow physics. In the work cited previously the authors investigate the effect of incoming wakes and free turbulence in the transition mechanisms of LPTs both numerically and experimentally.

The rotational effects on LPT transition and losses has never been properly addressed. Most of the detailed information on this ilk of flows is based on experimental non-rotating linear cascades. Moreover, the back to back analysis of rotating and non-rotating flows in annular cascades is technically difficult. Here, we study the effect of the Coriolis forces on the transition mechanism in isolation. This is in contrast to other studies such as that of Baum et al. [18] where the effect of the Coriolis force over the secondary flows is analysed. Thus, we consider a 3D blade cross-section and apply the Coriolis forces only to the perturbation with respect to the main flow. In this way the effect of the Coriolis force on the main flow is avoided and its effect on the instability mechanisms isolated. We do this with a compact high-order Flux Reconstruction method [19] without an explicit SGS model, i.e., we perform implicit LES (ILES) [20].

In this work we first describe the numerical method employed in the simulations and validate it against DNS of turbulent channel flows and experiments performed over a linear LPT cascade designed by ITP Aero and tested at UPM. We close this paper discussing the effect of the Coriolis forces on transition.

NOMENCLATURE

Roman symbols

\square^+	Quantity \square in wall units
\square^D	Discontinuous (not corrected) quantity \square
c_p	Pressure coefficient
c_x	Axial chord
F, G	Flux function in x, y direction
g_L, g_R	Left and right Radau polynomial
J	Determinant of the jacobian of coordinate transformation
L	Lagrange polynomial
p	Solution/polynomial order or static pressure
p_{t1}	Mean total pressure upstream of cascade
Re	Reynolds number
Ro	Rotational parameter
t	Time
U	Conservative quantity
V	Velocity
\tilde{V}	Element of standard element
x, y, z	Physical coordinates

Greek symbols

α_{ifl}	Lifting coefficient of element i , face f and face location l
$\gamma(\xi)$	Flux correction function
ξ, η	Coordinates in standard element
ρ_2	Mean density after cascade
Ω	Angular velocity

Abbreviations

BL	Boundary Layer
CFL	Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy
CPR	Correction Procedure by Reconstruction
DNS	Direct Numerical Simulation/Direct Navier Stokes
FR	Flux Reconstruction
ILES	Implicit LES
KH	Kelvin-Helmholz
LE	Leading Edge
LES	Large Eddy Simulation
LPT	Low Pressure Turbine
RANS	Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes
SGS	Sub-Grid Scale
SP	Solution Point
TE	Trailing Edge
uDNS	under-resolved DNS

NUMERICAL METHOD

Low numerical dissipation schemes are required for the simulation of turbulent flows due to the stringent requirements of accurate transport of vortical structures. Standard second-order methods suffer from high numerical dissipation and so the mesh requirements become very demanding. Higher-order compact numerical methods such as the Discontinuous Galerkin (DG), Spectral Volumes (SV) or the Flux Reconstruction (FR) offer low numerical dissipation and are, therefore, well suited for the simulation of vortical structures and turbulent flows ([20, 21]).

For the study of the present work we have developed a compressible high-order numerical solver that has been integrated as a new component of the ITP Aero in-house CFD suit called Mu^2s^2T [22, 23]. The solver is implemented using OpenCL to leverage GPU parallelism and MPI to allow using multiple GPUs in parallel. The high-order solver is based on the FR method of Huynh [19] and extended to triangular elements following the work of Wang and Gao [24]. This method has very low numerical dissipation which increases in the high-frequency range [21]. It is, therefore, very well suited for Large Eddy Simulations.

A summary of the numerical method is given next for completeness.

Spatial Discretisation

A summary of the FR method by Huynh [19] for the solution of 1D conservation equations, which can be written in compact form as:

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot F = 0 \quad (1)$$

is given first. Consider a 1D integration domain $\Omega = [0, L]$ discretised in N elements with the i th element defined by $V_i = [x_i, x_{i+1}]$. For each element i we define $p + 1$ solution points (SPs) at which the state variable (U) is evaluated. Given these

SPs the solution is approximated using Lagrange polynomials as

$$U(x, t) \approx U_i^h(x, t) = \sum_{j=1}^{p+1} U_{ij}^h(t) L_j(x) \quad (2)$$

where U_{ij}^h is the solution at SP j of element i , and $L_j(x)$ is the Lagrange polynomial with value 1 at $x = x_j$. For each element we define a local coordinate, $\xi = [-1, 1]$, such that $x_j = x_i + \frac{\Delta x_i}{2} (\xi_j + 1)$ with $\Delta x_i = x_{i+1} - x_i$. The flux function is defined in an analogous manner as:

$$F(U^h) \approx F_i^D(\xi, t) = \sum_{j=1}^{p+1} F(U_{ij}^h) L_j(\xi) \quad (3)$$

Since the solution is in general discontinuous across element interfaces we now seek to reconstruct the flux function in such a way that the reconstructed flux $F^C : i$ is of degree $p + 1$, that is one order higher than F^D ; ii is close to F^D ; and iii must take on the value of the interface fluxes at the boundaries of the element which is computed with a Riemann solver. The final corrected flux is of the form $F_i^C(\xi) = F_i^D(\xi) + \gamma_i(\xi)$ where $\gamma_i(\xi)$ is the correction flux function defined as:

$$\gamma_i(\xi) = [F_L^I - F^D(\xi = -1)] g_L(\xi) + [F_R^I - F^D(\xi = 1)] g_R(\xi) \quad (4)$$

where F_L^I and F_R^I are the left and right interface fluxes and $g_L(\xi)$ and $g_R(\xi)$ are the left and right correction functions. As noted in the original paper by Huynh [19] the choice of correction functions determines the properties of the discretisation. In our implementation, the left and right Radau polynomials are chosen. This is because more accurate solutions are recovered (albeit a somewhat more restrictive CFL condition is needed). This choice of correction functions recover the nodal-based discontinuous Galerkin formulation. The final discretised form of equation 1 is of the form:

$$\frac{\partial U}{\partial t} + \frac{d\xi}{dx} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^{p+1} F(U_{ij}^h) \frac{dL_j}{d\xi}(\xi) + [F_L^I - F^D(\xi = -1)] \frac{dg_L}{d\xi}(\xi) + [F_R^I - F^D(\xi = 1)] \frac{dg_R}{d\xi}(\xi) \right\} = 0 \quad (5)$$

which can be advanced in time with a time integration scheme.

The extension to multiple dimensions of the method is readily done for quadrilateral (QUAD) elements as tensor product operations in multiple dimensions. Since all derivative operations are made on the standard element ($\xi = [-1, 1]$ and $\eta = [-1, 1]$) equation 1 is rewritten in the standard element:

$$J \frac{\partial U}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \tilde{F}(U)}{\partial \xi} + \frac{\partial \tilde{G}(U)}{\partial \eta} = 0 \quad (6)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{F}(U) &= J(\xi_x F + \xi_y G) \\ \tilde{G}(U) &= J(\eta_x F + \eta_y G) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where J denotes the determinant of the jacobian matrix and ξ_x , ξ_y , η_x and η_y are the components of the inverse of the jacobian

matrix. The final discretised form becomes now:

$$J \frac{\partial U}{\partial t} + \sum_{m=0}^p \sum_{n=0}^p \tilde{F}_{mn}^D L'_m(\xi) L_n(\eta) + \sum_{m=0}^p \sum_{n=0}^p \tilde{G}_{mn}^D L_m(\xi) L'_n(\eta) + [\tilde{F}_L^I - \tilde{F}(-1, \eta)] g'_L(\xi) + [\tilde{F}_R^I - \tilde{F}(1, \eta)] g'_R(\xi) + [\tilde{G}_D^I - \tilde{G}(\xi, -1)] g'_L(\eta) + [\tilde{G}_U^I - \tilde{G}(\xi, 1)] g'_R(\eta) = 0 \quad (8)$$

where the subscripts D and U denote “down” and “upper”, respectively.

The extension of the method to triangular elements (TRIAs) can be made in several ways. We follow the Correction Procedure by Reconstruction (CPR) approach by Wang and Gao [24]. What follows are the final forms of the equations. For further insight into how to derive them the reader is referred to the original work [24].

Within the CPR framework equation 1 is discretised as follows in the reference triangle:

$$\frac{\partial \tilde{U}_i}{\partial t} + \tilde{\nabla} \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{F}}(U_i) + \frac{1}{\tilde{V}} \sum_{f \in \partial \tilde{V}} \sum_{l=0}^p \alpha_{ifl} [\tilde{F}^n]_{fl} \tilde{S}_f = 0 \quad (9)$$

where $\tilde{\nabla}$ denotes derivatives with respect to the computational spatial coordinates ξ, η ; $\tilde{U}_i = JU_i$; $\tilde{\mathbf{F}} = (\tilde{F}, \tilde{G})^T$; \tilde{V} is the area of the reference triangle; \tilde{S}_f is the length of the f side of the triangle; $[\tilde{F}^n]_{fl}$ denotes the normal jump of the flux function across the element interface at point l of side f ; and α_{ifl} represents the array of coefficients that determine the flux correction at SP i given a distribution of $[\tilde{F}^n]_{fl}$.

Temporal discretisation

Simulations of turbulent flows are unsteady in nature. In order to have meaningful results the order of the temporal integration errors should be kept equal or below the spatial-discretisation errors. In our simulations we use a polynomial order $p = 3$ so that our spatial discretisation error is of order $\mathcal{O}(\Delta x^4)$.

Our time integrator is the 4 stage fourth-order Runge Kutta. Due to the order of the temporal scheme and the small time-steps that result from stability conditions the time integration error is of much lower magnitude than that of the spatial discretisation.

Implicit LES

In Large Eddy Simulations (LES) one solves for the larger scales of motion while leaving the smaller scales to a SGS model. SGS models are based on the assumption of the smaller eddies being homogeneous and isotropic and hence having a behaviour independent of the larger scales of motion. In high-order upwinding schemes, such as our high-order Mu^2s^2T solver, the effect of the smaller scales is usually left to the numerical dissipation. Because no explicit SGS model is used these type of simulations fall under the fields of the Implicit LES (ILES)

or under-resolved Direct Numerical Simulations (uDNS) [20]. Despite ILES being criticised by some it has been proven to be adequate for turbulent flow simulations [20] and can even out-perform schemes with explicit SGS model [25].

Because not all turbulent scales are modelled the grid requirements in LES are relaxed with respect to DNS even though grid requirements near the wall remain considerably stringent. For instance, in [14] Ameri reviews the wall grid spacing of several LES computations of LPTs and considers a choice of wall grid spacings $\Delta y^+ \simeq 1$, $\Delta x^+ \simeq 10$ and $\Delta z^+ \simeq 24$ (x is the mean-flow direction and y and z are the wall normal- and span-directions respectively) which are in agreement with the guidelines given in [26] by Piomelli and Chasnov for resolved LES simulations. With this wall grid resolution Ameri [14] achieves good overall agreement with experiments.

This study is based on implicit LES since we do not solve all scales of turbulence and the numerical dissipation is the responsible to account for the effect of the smaller scales.

VALIDATION CASES

Two validation cases are considered here: the turbulent channel flow and experimental results of linear cascade.

In the former case we compare our results against the DNS data from Lee et al. [27] whereas for the latter we compare against experimental data of a linear LPT cascade designed at ITP Aero and tested at UPM.

Turbulent channel flow

The fully developed turbulent channel flow case has been used as a validation case by other authors, e.g., Carton & Hillewaert [28]. This case features the flow between two parallel walls at a distance of 2δ from each other. In our case, the mean flow is aligned with the x -direction, the lower and upper walls are at $y = 0$ and $y = 2\delta$ respectively and z is the span-wise direction. Periodicity is assumed in the stream- and span-wise directions so that a forcing term representing the stream-wise pressure gradient is added to the equations to set the mean flow. This is an ideal test-case since no inlet or outlet boundary conditions need to be specified hence significantly reducing the number of uncertainties.

In order to keep the cost of the simulations low we have run the lowest Reynolds number out of the DNS data in [27], i.e., $Re_\tau = 180$. The friction Reynolds number is defined as $Re_\tau = \rho u_\tau \delta / \mu$ where the friction velocity, u_τ , is defined as $u_\tau^2 = \tau_w / \rho$ and τ_w is the shear stress at the wall, $\tau_w = \mu \frac{\partial u}{\partial y}$. Additionally, we have used a rather coarse mesh with 41 equally spaced elements in each direction and the physical computational box is $L_x = 2\pi\delta$, $L_y = 2\delta$ and $L_z = \pi\delta$ in the x , y and z directions, respectively, which is smaller than that used by Lee and Moser in [27] ($L_x = 8\pi\delta$, $L_y = 2\delta$ and $L_z = 3\pi\delta$). At the Re_τ

FIGURE 1. Autocorrelation in the span-wise direction of the axial velocity at a mid channel height.

considered here the span of the channel is sufficiently large to allow for the stream-wise streaks (whose length near the wall is about 100 wall units) to develop, however, their dynamics can be affected at the mid-channel height and may potentially affect the logarithmic region. Figure 1 shows the autocorrelation of axial velocity at mid-channel height in the span-wise direction. As seen in the figure, no correlation is shown across the span which means that the span considered here ($\pi\delta$) does not allow for structures larger than half the span to develop.

Figure 2 compares the mean velocity profile obtained with the Mu^2s^2T (4th order solution) against the DNS results [27]. Our results are in remarkable good agreement with the DNS data, especially considering the fact that we have used a smaller computational box. It is also worth noting that the first element is located in the buffer region ($y^+ = 8.48$) between the viscous and the logarithmic sub-layers and that the first inner point is in $y^+ = 2.34$ which is above the standard recommended values ($y^+ < 2$) [26]. Minor differences with the DNS data can be seen in the logarithmic region most likely due to the size of the computational box, as mentioned above.

A simulation with $Re_\tau = 325$ was run using the same computational box. Running a higher Reynolds makes the box size more suitable but makes the mesh resolution even coarser. Figure 2 shows the results obtained along with the DNS results for $Re_\tau = 550$ (for clarity of the figure the results have been shifted in the positive direction with a $\Delta u^+ = 5$). In this case the first

FIGURE 2. Mean velocity profile in wall units for several Reynolds numbers along with the log law $u^+ = 1/0.41 \log(y^+) + 5.0$ (dashed line). For clarity the DNS solution at $Re_\tau = 550$ (green line), the LES solution at $Re_\tau = 325$ (circles) and an additional log-law curve have been shifted upward with $\Delta u^+ = 5$.

element again lays within the buffer sub-layer and the first point of this element off the wall is at $y^+ = 4.19$, i.e., almost out of the viscous sub-layer. As seen, even with this coarser mesh the mean velocity profile follows the log-law and compares well with the DNS results considering these are at a higher Re_τ which shift the logarithmic region slightly [27].

Figure 3 shows the root-mean-square of the velocity fluctuations. Again here excellent agreement between the DNS [27] and our LES is seen despite the use of a computational box with marginal resolution.

In summary, even though a larger computational box should be run, the results show that the code is well-suited to perform LES of turbulent flows.

Linear cascade

A generic LPT research section, tested at the Fluid Dynamics Laboratory of the UPM was used, for comparison purposes. The approaching velocity of the flow is very low and the flow can be considered incompressible. The inlet angle of the simulations is $\alpha_1 = 34$ and the pitch to chord ratio 1.3. The airfoil is highly loaded and the suction peak is at about 30% of the axial chord (c_x). The total turning is about 90° .

FIGURE 3. Comparison of the root-mean-square values of the velocity fluctuations for $Re_\tau = 180$. \circ Mu^2s^2T values; lines are DNS by Lee and Moser[27].

The experimental facility used in the study is the unsteady low-speed linear cascade rig available at Universidad Politécnicade Madrid (UPM). It operates as an open return, impulse wind tunnel. The approaching flow has a 495x240 mm rectangular cross-section. Prior to the test section, conditioning elements are included to ensure the proper quality of the cascade approaching flow.

The rig is operated in a closed test-cell that can be isotropically seeded with oil steam, enabling laser based velocimetry diagnostics. For that purpose, the test section is built in perspex. A mechanism is included to allow unsteady studies where the linear cascade is exposed to upstream generated wakes shed from uniformly spaced bars, which are displaced by a computer controlled electric motor. The moving bars mechanism follows a design similar to other existing facilities [29]. Flow diagnostics available in the experimental facility include wall pressure characterisation, inlet to outlet total pressure loss measurements, and temporally resolved anemometry through hot-wire, laser-Doppler, and PIV velocimetry.

Tests were carried out at several Reynolds numbers, e.g., $Re = 50000$, 100000 and 200000 ; for several incidence angles and wake-passing frequencies. We present here results for the clean case (without passing bars) and $Re = 5 \cdot 10^4$ and $Re = 10^5$.

Figure 4 shows a cross-section of the mesh used for the $Re = 10^5$ case being the topology of the $Re = 5 \cdot 10^4$ case very similar

FIGURE 4. Mesh cross-section around the profile (Top) and a detail of the aft portion (Bottom) used for the $Re = 10^5$ case.

FIGURE 5. Pressure coefficient of the low-pressure cascade at $Re = 5 \cdot 10^4$ and $Re = 10^5$. Experimental data (circles) and results obtained with Mu^2s^2T (lines).

to that presented in the figure. A detail of the mesh around the aft portion of the profile is also shown in the same figure. It can be seen that the mesh is finer around the area where the separation bubble and transition occur as well as a region downstream of the trailing edge so that the wake can be accurately simulated up to a distance of 25% of the axial chord in the x direction. It must be reminded that a high-order code is used and so each cell seen in figure 4 has additional (internal) points (not seen in the figure).

For the $Re = 5 \cdot 10^4$ case the 2D section is extruded in the span direction a distance of $0.4c_x$ and discretised with 40 elements along that direction (note that 4th order elements have 4 points in the span direction). This results in a mesh with 25M computational points which, after collapsing repeated nodes, yields a mesh with 9.7M physical points. At the wall the mesh spacing in wall units results in $\Delta y^+ < 1$, $\Delta x^+ < 15$ and $\Delta z^+ < 12$ which are lower than the values recommended by Piomelli and Chasnov in [26] for wall-resolved LES ($\Delta y^+ < 2$, $\Delta x^+ \simeq 50 - 150$ and $\Delta z^+ \simeq 15 - 40$).

For the $Re = 10^5$ case the 2D section is extruded in the span direction a distance of $0.2c_x$ and discretised with 40 elements along that direction. This results in a mesh with 40M computational points which, after collapsing repeated nodes, yields a mesh with 16M physical points. At the wall the mesh spacing in wall units results in $\Delta y^+ < 0.6$, $\Delta x^+ < 11$ and $\Delta z^+ < 17$ which are, again, lower than the values recommended by Piomelli and Chasnov in [26] for wall-resolved LES. Further, we would like the reader to note that a 4th order method is being used here and so our mesh is extremely fine for wall-resolved LES.

Periodic boundary conditions (BC) are used in the span-direction so that results are representative of the experiment mid-section. Periodic BC are also used in the pitch direction and only one airfoil of the cascade is simulated. Because basic inlet/outlet conditions are imposed at inlet/outlet a coarse mesh region before and after the profile is included to work as buffer region and prevent spurious reflections. No inlet turbulence is considered since the wind-tunnel inlet turbulent intensity is very low ($< 0.1\%$). However, our basic inlet condition generates reflections which are not entirely damped out in the buffer region.

An initial simulation is done starting from a RANS solution and run for 4 flow-through times in order to achieve a quasi-steady state solution. This is taken as the initial solution and it is run for 6 more flow-through times (33.6/96 hours on 40GPUs for the $Re = 5 \cdot 10^4/Re = 10^5$ case).

Figure 5 shows the pressure coefficient along the axial direction for the experiments and our numerical results. As seen in the figure, at these Reynolds numbers a laminar separation bubble forms on the suction side with reattachment before the trailing edge. Over the separated region a shear layer with inflectional (unstable) velocity distribution forms which rolls up (KH instabilities) and rapidly transitions to turbulence due to the breakdown of KH waves. This is a typical transition process of modern LPTs at low Reynolds number as explained in detail by

FIGURE 6. Mean turbulent kinetic energy for base (Top) and Coriolis (Bottom) cases at $Re = 5 \cdot 10^4$. The white line indicates the position of the bubble. The white dashed line marks the maximum of the mean turbulent kinetic energy of the Coriolis case.

Coull and Hodson in [2]. At higher Reynolds numbers transition occurs earlier and the bubble closes further upstream. This behaviour is well captured by our numerical simulations though differences are observed in the location of the reattachment point. We suspect this effect might be due to upstream perturbations generated by our simplistic inlet boundary conditions.

Wind-tunnel effects such as boundary layer growth and blowing through holes (such as those used to run the passing bars) are taken into account including in the governing equations modifications where the streamtube contraction/expansion is accounted for. These additional terms in the equations are only applied between the axial planes delimiting the airfoil. This allows us to match the pressure coefficient in the leading and trailing edges.

In summary, the overall agreement between numerical and experimental results is very good despite a clear mismatch in the location of the reattachment points. We believe this could be due to spurious undamped reflections in the boundary conditions.

FIGURE 9. Boundary Layer profile around bubble. Top: Mean boundary layer velocity distribution along the vertical direction at several stream-wise locations. Bottom: Root mean square velocity fluctuations in the x (solid lines) and y (dashed lines) directions at several streamwise locations. Relative the bubble the locations are as follows: $x/c_x = 0.5$ is before the bubble; $x/c_x = 0.57$ is near the separation point; $x/c_x = 0.74$ is in the bubble; $x/c_x = 0.87$ is near the reattachment point; and $x/c_x = 0.97$ is aft of the bubble.

CORIOLIS EFFECTS

In this section we investigate the effect of the Coriolis forces on the transition mechanism of a LPT airfoil. The Coriolis forces are applied only to the velocity perturbations so that no mean flow (secondary flow) is generated:

$$F_{\text{coriolis}} = -2\Omega \times (V - \bar{V}) \quad (10)$$

where Ω is the rotational speed, V is the speed and \bar{V} is the time averaged speed. We have chosen a value of Ω such that the rotational parameter defined as

$$Ro = \frac{\Omega c_x}{V_2} \quad (11)$$

takes the value of 1 (V_2 is the outlet mean velocity).

In what follows we present the results for the $Re = 5 \cdot 10^4$ case. Results for the $Re = 10^5$ case are very similar.

Figure 6 shows the contour plots of mean turbulent kinetic energy at the aft of the airfoil for both baseline and Coriolis cases for the $Re = 5 \cdot 10^4$ case. The white line in the figure marks the

limit of the reversed flow region (the laminar separation bubble). It can be seen that the bubble length and the turbulent kinetic energy remain almost unchanged. Although barely appreciable in the figure the peak in turbulent kinetic energy (which happens close to the reattachment point [16]) has moved slightly upstream for the case with Coriolis forces (white dashed line) with respect to the baseline case. This effect can be due to an increased instability of the span-wise vortices generated by the roll-up of the shear layer. Figure 7 demonstrates this. This figure depicts iso-surfaces of pressure perturbations (p') in a similar fashion as what is done by McAuliffe&Yaras in [16]. It can be seen in figure 7 that, for the baseline case, the span-wise vortices are initially two-dimensional and break down downstream of the reattachment point. In contrast, in the Coriolis case, span-wise vortices are three-dimensional in nature from the very onset of the instability, i.e., the transition point is moved upstream. This could potentially increase skin-friction and lead to higher losses though in this case differences in skin-friction are negligible pos-

FIGURE 7. Isosurfaces of p' for the baseline (Top) and Coriolis (Bottom) cases at $Re = 5 \cdot 10^4$. The white line denotes the position of the separation bubble. Red denotes higher pressures than the average whereas purple denotes lower than average pressure..

sibly because of the low Reynolds number and the meagre difference between the separation points.

Because of the limited effect of the Coriolis forces on the reattachment flow the pressure distribution over the profile changes very little. This is seen in figure 8 where the pressure coefficient over the airfoil for both the baseline and the Coriolis cases at $Re = 5 \cdot 10^4$ are plotted. The focus is given in this figure to the reattachment region where it is seen that, indeed, a minor difference is seen in the bubble length.

Figure 9 shows the boundary layer profile (velocities and fluctuations) at several locations around the bubble: location $x/c_x = 0.5$ is before the bubble; $x/c_x = 0.57$ is near the separation point; $x/c_x = 0.74$ is in the bubble; $x/c_x = 0.87$ is near the reattachment point; and $x/c_x = 0.97$ is aft of the bubble. The velocity profile follows an evolution typical of boundary layers with adverse pressure gradient (APG), i.e., the (almost) linear near-wall profile at $x/c_x = 0.5$ becomes inflectional due to the APG and eventually separates at around $x/c_x = 0.57$ where the normal derivative of the stream-wise velocity becomes zero. Within the bubble ($x/c_x = 0.74$) the profile is still inflectional

FIGURE 8. Detail around the reattachment point of the distribution of pressure coefficient for the Baseline and Coriolis case at $Re = 5 \cdot 10^4$.

FIGURE 10. Distribution of root-mean-square of shear stress in xy ($u'v'$) at 25% of the axial chord downstream of the trailing edge for the baseline and Coriolis cases at $Re = 5 \cdot 10^4$. The total pressure profile is also plotted here for reference.

(unstable) with negative velocity inside the bubble. Instabilities spark transition to turbulence and reattachment of the flow ($x/c_x = 0.87$). That the flow has become turbulent at reattachment ($x/c_x = 0.87$) can be seen in the lower row of figure 9 where root mean square values of the velocity fluctuations are plotted. Turbulence injects momentum into the boundary layer and so a fuller velocity profile can be seen downstream of the reattachment point ($x/c_x = 0.97$). As seen in the figure the mean velocity profile is barely affected. The effect of the Coriolis forces over the fluctuations varies along the normal direction. It seems like after the reattachment point the Coriolis forces redistributes the Reynolds stresses such that peak value of the fluctuations is reduced. Nevertheless, the effects are very small.

We have discussed so far how the Coriolis force influences transition to turbulence. We now discuss the effect on the turbulent wake. Figure 10 (Top) shows the mean pitch-wise distribution of total pressure at a distance of 25% of the axial chord (c_x) downstream of the airfoil. It is apparent in this figure that the total pressure distribution is different for the baseline and coriolis cases. This would indicate that the mixing between the free stream and the wake is affected by the Coriolis force. Looking at the shear stress should give an indication of the mixing in the wake. Figure 10 (Bottom) shows the shear stress at $0.25c_x$ downstream of the trailing edge for $Re = 5 \cdot 10^4$. It is evident from the figure that the higher statistics are not fully converged. However, this figure does give an idea of what is the amount of mixing. Until about a pitch-wise position $y/pitch = 0.4$ the shear stress in the Coriolis case is higher and so the total pressure for this case remains higher than that of the baseline case. From this point onwards the situation is reversed and the total pressure of the baseline case remains higher. This is, the Coriolis force seems to increase mixing in the pressure side of the wake whereas decreases it on the suction side of the wake. The net effect is an increase in total pressure losses of 3.6%.

Overall, Coriolis forces advance the onset of turbulence, modify the mixing in the wake and increase the total pressure losses. Their effect is, however, limited for the present configuration.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

A high-order numerical code has been presented in this work. The spatial discretisation is based on the Flux Reconstruction method which allows for arbitrary precision (p refinement). This method is upwinding in nature and so no SGS model is needed to perform LES studies (ILES).

This code has been validated against DNS and experimental data. The classical turbulent channel flow has been simulated at a low Reynolds number ($Re_\tau = 180$). A shorter than the required computational box and a coarse grid have been used yielding very precise results. The differences between the DNS data and our simulations are attributed to the too small computational

box. Using the same mesh as for the $Re_\tau = 180$ case a simulation has also been run for $Re_\tau = 550$ resulting in an even coarser mesh and, yet, giving very accurate results. Accurate results can be obtained with values of y^+ up to 4.2 (with polynomial order 3).

Comparisons against the experimental data of an LPT at $Re = 5 \cdot 10^4$ and $Re = 10^5$ is also very good. Despite the mismatch between experiments and simulations in the reattachment points the simulations do capture the trend with variations of Reynolds number. Differences have been attributed to the streamtube correction and to simplistic inlet boundary conditions which generate spurious perturbations (partly removed by buffer regions).

Using this tool we have studied the effect of the Coriolis force in isolation on the transition process. We have done this by applying this force only to the perturbations with respect to the mean field. This avoids the formation of secondary flows and allows us to do this on a 3D cross-section. Despite the low value of the rotational speed it is seen that transition to turbulence is accelerated by further destabilising the Kelvin-Helmholz vortices. Reattachment, however, is barely modified.

Along the wake, Coriolis forces seem to increase mixing in the pressure side of the wake whereas it reduces it on the suction side. Overall, the Coriolis force increases the losses.

This study has been performed neglecting span-wise pressure gradients and, therefore, it outlines which is the minimum level of perturbation in the flow induced by Coriolis forces.

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